

ISic1357

I.Sicily inscription 1357

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015.10.22

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 8744

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140861

1. πρ (ὀ) ς' καλανδ [ῶν]
2. Ἰουνίων ξ [γῶ]
3. Θέδουλος
4. ζῶν κὲ εἰμέ-
5. νος ἡγόρασα
6. παρὰ Ἀρίστωνος.
- 7.

Edition: PHI340017

1. ζῶν κείμε-
2. νος ²⁶κείμενος²⁶ ἡγόρασα
- 3.

Edition: PHI340018

1. ζῶν κὲ εἰμέ-
2. νος ἡγόρασα
- 3.

Edition: PHI340019

1. ζῶν κὲ [κ]είμε-
2. νος ἡγόρασα
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

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Bibliography

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